

Review article

CaCO₃ crystals as versatile carriers for controlled delivery of antimicrobialsAna M. Ferreira^a, Anna S. Vikulina^b, Dmitry Volodkin^{a,*}^a School of Science and Technology, Department of Chemistry and Forensics, Nottingham Trent University, Clifton Lane, Nottingham NG11 8NS, UK^b Fraunhofer Institute for Cell Therapy and Immunology, Branch Bioanalytics and Bioprocesses, Am Mühlenberg 13, Potsdam, Golm 14476, Germany

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ABSTRACT

CaCO₃ crystals have been known for a long time as naturally derived and simply fabricated nano(micro)-sized materials able to effectively host and release various molecules. This review summarises the use of CaCO₃ crystals as versatile carriers to host, protect and release antimicrobials, offering a strong tool to tackle antimicrobial resistance, a serious global health problem. The main methods for the synthesis of CaCO₃ crystals with different properties, as well as the approaches for the loading and release of antimicrobials are presented. Finally, prospects to utilize the crystals in order to improve the therapeutic outcome and combat antimicrobial resistance are highlighted. Ultimately, this review intends to provide an in-depth overview of the application of CaCO₃ crystals for the smart and controlled delivery of antimicrobial agents and aims at identifying the advantages and drawbacks as well as guiding future works, research directions and industrial applications.

1. Introduction

The discovery of the first antibiotics marked a turning point in the history of medicine. The prospects of cure for patients with bacterial infections changed radically for the best. However, antimicrobials heavy and sometimes incorrect use promoted the appearance of alarming levels of resistance. Antibiotic-resistant infections cause per year at least 25,000 deaths in the European Union [1] and 35,000 in the United States of America [2], with the prospects of causing 10 million deaths globally per year by 2050 if nothing is done to address the problem [3]. The lack of new classes of antibiotics in the market, and the lower interest of pharmaceutical companies in developing new drugs (low success and profits) accentuates the severity of the problem [4–6].

The rational use of antibiotics is essential to tackle the levels of bacterial resistance. Numerous campaigns and discussion groups have been created to raise the attention of healthcare practitioners and the general public, nonetheless there is still a long way to go.

Drug delivery systems are extremely important to improve the pharmacokinetics of antimicrobials, antimicrobial activity, patients' adherence to treatment programs, decrease side effects, and suppress the appearance of new resistance mechanisms [7–10].

The antibiotics used clinically today present some drawbacks such as limited stability (due to variation of temperature and pH, presence of chelating agents), solubility, bioavailability, distribution/penetration in the target tissue, and short half-lives [6,8,11]. Moreover, new

therapeutic agents, e.g. antimicrobial peptides, are sensitive to enzymatic decomposition [12].

In an attempt to improve drug delivery effectiveness and the chemotherapeutic outcomes, new carriers have been developed to effectively deliver antimicrobials. These include mesoporous silica, liposomes, quantum dots, dendrimers, solid lipid nanoparticles, nano- and micro-emulsions, gels, carbon nanomaterials, magnetic nanoparticles, microneedles and polymeric microparticles [13–17]. The popular polymer-based carriers are typically made of polymers such as chitosan, alginate, gelatin, albumin, collagen, poly(vinyl pyrrolidone), poly(acrylic acid), poly(vinyl alcohol), poly(methyl methacrylate), polyurethanes, polystyrene, poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid), poly(lactic acid) and polyglycolic acid, with the last three being the most studied [16–19]. Some of the delivery carriers enumerated are already used in commercialized products [18,19]. However, the often intricate and multi-step production, cytotoxicity, recognition by the immune system, and significant loss of bioactivity in the complex biological media retards their further clinical translation and urges the search for alternative carriers that can bypass these limitations [13,20].

CaCO₃ is a versatile mineral with different applications such as construction (limestone), bone cements, dental implants, scaffolds, filler for paints, coatings, paper, pigments and plastics [21–24]. CaCO₃ is also included in different pharmacopoeias and is widely commercialized for pharmaceutical use in oral formulations as an excipient/active substance (antacids and medicines for the treatment of calcium deficiency). More recently it has been employed as a vector for drug

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delivery and as a decomposable template for assembly of multilayer capsules [21,22,25,26]. CaCO_3 availability, low price, biocompatibility, biodegradability, high surface area, simple synthesis, tuneable and stimuli-responsive properties, make it an excellent candidate for loading and controlled release of various drugs [27]. Importantly, the use of calcium carbonate as a food and pharmaceutical additive/ingredient is approved by the Food and Drug Administration Agency (FDA). Recently, the European Food Safety Agency Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food, re-evaluated its usage taking into account the latest available toxicological data and confirmed no toxicological concerns for the use of CaCO_3 [28]. Numerous works have reported the use of CaCO_3 , mainly the vaterite polymorph, for biomedical applications, e.g., for encapsulation of enzymes, hormones, DNA, growth factors, and drugs [21,29–41]. The employment CaCO_3 crystals as carriers for delivery of antimicrobials was demonstrated for the first time about 16 years ago and was followed by several scientific reports demonstrating the advantages of CaCO_3 crystals for antimicrobials delivery over other drug delivery systems. CaCO_3 protects the antimicrobial agents from the external environment and can be designed to release the cargo in a controlled way and on demand. One of the most interesting characteristics of the CaCO_3 crystals is their sensitivity to different pH values which allows the cargo to be released on specific sites or conditions without affecting the antimicrobial activity. Moreover, the easily adjustable properties of CaCO_3 crystals (size, solubility, shape, composition) makes them attractive and dynamic drug delivery systems for different targets, microenvironment conditions and routes of administration.

This review summarises the use of CaCO_3 nano- and micro-crystals as versatile carriers to deliver antimicrobials in a controlled and programmed manner as highly desired for multiple drug delivery applications. The first part of this review intends to look at the main synthesis routes of CaCO_3 crystals and the factors that affect the crystal properties (e.g. size, morphology, structure) and can be used to fine tune CaCO_3 crystals properties. In the second part, the approaches for loading/release of antimicrobials into/from the crystals and the antimicrobial performance of CaCO_3 crystals are addressed. In the end of the review, the outlooks for better therapeutic outcome and effective tackling of the antimicrobial resistance using CaCO_3 crystals are given (Fig. 1).

2. CaCO_3 crystals

CaCO_3 is a mineral that occurs in three anhydrous crystalline forms (aragonite, vaterite and calcite) and two hydrated crystalline forms with limited occurrence, i.e., ikaite and monohydrocalcite [42,43]. CaCO_3 can also occur as amorphous CaCO_3 (ACC), which is highly unstable and rapidly transforms into the metastable or stable polymorphs. Calcite is the most thermodynamically stable polymorph at standard conditions, and like the other anhydrous polymorphs, ACC precedes its formation [43,44].

Each CaCO_3 anhydrous polymorph has a typical morphology. Aragonite presents a needle-like shape, while vaterite and calcite have a spherical and rhombohedral morphology, respectively (Fig. 2) [45]. Nonetheless, this shape can be changed by altering different synthesis conditions [22].

Bare vaterite crystals are unstable in aqueous solutions recrystallizing to calcite within some hours or a few days; this can, however, be affected by the presence of additives like nanoparticles and different types of polymers [21,22,48,49]. Despite this, its porous structure, high surface area, tunable morphology, size (which can range from tens of nanometres to tens of micrometres) and recrystallization kinetic, makes it an attractive drug carrier [21,50]. From all the CaCO_3 polymorphs vaterite presents the best properties for drug delivery, nonetheless, being a metastable phase between ACC and calcite, it poses some challenges and opportunities. These are related to keeping vaterite stable and maintaining its porous structure, but also using vaterite “limitations” as triggers for drug delivery, i.e. recrystallization to calcite and pH sensitivity.

2.1. Main routes of CaCO_3 synthesis

There are four main CaCO_3 synthesis methods: CO_2 bubbling, slow carbonation, reverse emulsion and solution precipitation (Fig. 3) [51,52]. CO_2 bubbling or carbonation is the main industrial method and consists of bubbling CO_2 in a $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ solution (Eq. (3) and Eq. (4)) obtained from limestone calcination (Eq. (1)) followed by hydration (Eq. (2)) [53–55]. This method results mainly in nano-sized calcite crystals [22,56], nonetheless the size, polymorph type, morphology and properties of the formed particles can be controlled by adding additives, changing the Ca^{2+} concentration, or the operating conditions such as liquid or gas flow rate, CO_2 pressure and temperature [22].

Fig. 1. Outline of the main topics covered in this review.

Fig. 2. SEM images of aragonite (A), broken vaterite (B), vaterite and vaterite recrystallizing to calcite (C) and calcite (D). Image A adapted from Lucas et al. [46] and Images B, C, D from Volodkin D. et al. [47]. Copyright 2001, with permissions from Elsevier (Image A) and Copyright 2004, with permission from American Chemical Society (Image B, C and D).

Slow carbonation reaction is another carbonation method which is less applied. It consists of the production of carbonate ions through the dissolution of CO_2 resultant from the slow hydrolysis of dimethyl carbonate, ammonium carbonate, or other compounds (Eq. (5)), under

alkaline conditions [22,57–59].

Reverse emulsion (water in oil or W/O) synthesis comprises a system composed of a hydrophobic continuous phase with dispersed hydrophilic droplets (CO_3^{2-} or Ca^{2+} solutions) stabilized by a surfactant. CaCO_3 is formed when the emulsions are mixed, and the micelles containing CO_3^{2-} and Ca^{2+} ions collide, forming “micro-reactors”. This method allows the synthesis of nano- and micro-particles with narrow size distributions. The type of CaCO_3 polymorph, size and morphology

Fig. 3. Main CaCO_3 synthesis methods: (a) solution precipitation method; (b) reverse emulsion (W/O) method; (c) CO_2 bubbling method and (d) slow carbonation method. Figure redrawn based on the work of Boyjoo et al. [22].

of the crystals can be controlled by adding different additives, changing the pH, temperature, reaction time as well as the molar ratios of water to oil, water to surfactant, and Ca^{2+} to CO_3^{2-} [22,60].

The solution route, also known as solution precipitation method or mixing method [61], is the main method used on a lab-scale, and comprises the mixing of supersaturated solutions of CO_3^{2-} and Ca^{2+} containing salts with or without additives. It is the simplest and quickest method, when compared with the carbonation or reverse emulsion, and the modification of different synthesis variables allows to adjust the size, shape, and type of polymorph synthesized. Up to the best of our knowledge, nowadays, only this method has been up scaled for commercial fabrication of vaterite microcrystals (e.g. PlasmaChem GmbH, Germany). In relation to the encapsulation of antimicrobials, the solution precipitation method has received the most widespread use up to now.

2.2. Synthesis conditions effect on CaCO_3 crystals

Various synthesis conditions like presence of additives, solvent type, pH, rate and mode of component mixing, temperature and precursor concentrations can significantly affect the properties of the crystals. Notably, the effect of most of these synthesis conditions, like pH, supersaturation, temperature, mixing mode and solvents, are transversal to the majority of the synthesis/loading methods. Most of these variables have been extensively studied, and the best conditions to produce crystals with specific size, polymorph form, or other required properties have been determined. In the sections below, the effect of these variables will be addressed in more detail, with a special focus on the solution precipitation method, due to its widespread use and the high number of detailed studies.

2.2.1. pH

The main effect of pH is on the availability of carbonate ions. At $\text{pH} \leq 8$, carbonate ions are mainly protonated to bicarbonate, decreasing CO_3^{2-} concentration, and consequently interfering with the precipitation of CaCO_3 . Therefore, pH values above 8 are necessary for CaCO_3 synthesis. However, within the basic pH range, very high pH values create high nucleation rates, promoting uncontrolled crystal growth and the formation of large and irregular crystals [22].

The pH value also governs the effect of some additives, mainly when they possess ionizable groups, e.g., carboxyl group which is ionized at basic pH and originates sites able to interact with Ca^{2+} controlling the formation of the crystals and resulting in particles with a more uniform size distribution [22].

Oral et al. [62] studied the influence of pH on CaCO_3 synthesis at room temperature, through the solution precipitation method in the presence of ethylene glycol (EG). The results demonstrated that vaterite particles formed independently of the $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]:[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$ ratio, when the pH of the precursor solutions was 8 and 10. However, above pH 10, the ratio of the salts started to play a role in the type of polymorph formed. Oral and co-workers verified that the size of CaCO_3 particles increased with an increase in the pH of the precursor solutions.

Clifford Y. et al. [63] studied the effect of different synthesis conditions, including pH, on the polymorphism of CaCO_3 using a constant-composition method. The experiment comprised mixing solutions of CaCl_2 with Na_2CO_3 at constant conditions. The authors demonstrated the effect of pH on the type of polymorph formed and that vaterite is the main polymorph formed between pH 8.5 and 10 at 24 °C.

Han Y. et al. [64] studied the effect of pH on the type of polymorph formed by the carbonation method and, overall, it was also demonstrated that higher pH values resulted in a decrease of the vaterite fraction (Fig. 4) in favour of calcite.

2.2.2. Temperature

Temperature is an important factor when synthesizing CaCO_3 crystals, as it influences the polymorphism of the particles produced

Fig. 4. Fraction of vaterite at different pH values. Synthesis based on passing CO_2/N_2 mixed gas into a CaCl_2 solution at 20 °C. Reprinted from Han Y. et al. [64]. Copyright 2006, with permission from Elsevier.

[65]. Ogino et al. [66] synthesized CaCO_3 particles by mixing CaCl_2 (1.93×10^{-2} M) with Na_2CO_3 (9.26×10^{-3} M) at a molar ratio of 2 to 1, respectively, and studied the effect of temperature on the type of polymorph formed. Ogino T. and co-workers verified that at low temperatures (≤ 20 °C) calcite is the main polymorph formed, while between 30 and 40 °C vaterite is produced at higher contents, and at temperatures around 70 °C aragonite is the predominant polymorph. Similar findings were reported by Chen et al. [67], who synthesized CaCO_3 by mixing CaCl_2 (0.25 M) and NH_4HCO_3 (0.25 M) (Fig. 5). Nonetheless, in contrast to the work of Ogino et al. [66], the formation of vaterite was also observed at 60 °C. Ševčík R. et al. [68], also reported the synthesis of vaterite at 60 °C by mixing equal molar ratios of CaCl_2 (2.0 M) and K_2CO_3 (2.0 M). This difference can be explained by the higher molar ratios used by Ševčík R. et al. [68] and Chen et al. [67]. This demonstrates that the initial concentration of the reagents can modulate the temperature effect on the type of polymorph formed. This effect was previously reported by Ma et al. [65].

Interestingly, the temperature during synthesis of vaterite polymorph affects its mesoporous internal structure. Feoktistova et al. [25], verified that vaterite crystals synthesized without additives at higher temperatures (45 °C) present larger pore size, a property that might be crucial for many bio-applications.

2.2.3. Supersaturation and $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]:[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$ ratio

The concentration of the precursor salts and the $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]:[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$ ratio affect the synthesis duration, type, and size of the polymorph formed. The crystallization takes place just when the supersaturation is reached. The high supersaturation results in higher nucleation ratios and lower induction times [69]. According to the “Ostwald’s step rule” at a low supersaturation the stable polymorph (calcite) may preferentially precipitate while at a high supersaturation the metastable polymorph (vaterite and aragonite) tends to form [70,71]. Kitamura [70] verified this tendency when synthesizing CaCO_3 by mixing CaCl_2 and Na_2CO_3 solutions at different concentrations at ca 25 °C. It was shown that vaterite tends to precipitate at a high supersaturation (200 mM) while calcite mainly precipitates at a lower concentration (50 mM) [70]. The same trend was verified by Ma et al. [65] and Ogino et al. [66], who reported that the relative abundance of vaterite increased by increasing the concentrations of calcium and carbonate ions at 25 °C. Nonetheless, it has been demonstrated that when the supersaturation of ACC is lower than 1, i.e. the ion activity product of the initial supersaturated solution is lower than the solubility product of ACC at 25 °C, only vaterite crystals are formed and present a peculiar

Fig. 5. Polymorphic abundance (%) of crystalline carbonates at the early metastable stages as a function of temperature. 1 - vaterite; 2 - aragonite and 3 - calcite. Adapted from Ogino et al. [66] (left) and Chen et al. [67] (right). Copyright 1987 and 2009, respectively, with permission from Elsevier.

hexagonal plate-like shape [66,72]. Moreover, the synthesis of these vaterite crystals implies longer induction times (time needed for the detection of the first newly created particles) due to the low initial concentrations (c_i) of the salts solutions: $c_i(\text{Ca}^{2+}) = c_i(\text{CO}_3^{2-}) < 1.8 \text{ mM}$ [72]. The supersaturation rate also influences the size of CaCO_3 crystals. Higher supersaturation promotes the formation of smaller crystals due to a higher nucleation rate at the same total mass of the precipitate [50,61,70].

Finally, the ratio of the precursor salt affects mainly the size and shape of the crystals. Nonetheless, at a very high pH value it can also affect the type of polymorph formed [62]. It has been demonstrated that higher concentrations of CO_3^{2-} ions, in comparison with Ca^{2+} ions, result in the formation of crystals with more ellipsoidal geometries while lower concentrations promote the formation of isotropic spherical particles (Fig. 6) [62,73].

2.2.4. Reagent mixing

The reagents mixing order and stirring speed affect mainly the morphology, size and size distribution of the crystals [22]. Volodkin D. et al. [74] tested the effect of the stirring time (15, 20, 30 and 40 s) and speed (400, 650 and 900 rpm) on the synthesis of CaCO_3 by the solution

Fig. 6. Dependence of particle ellipticity on the $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]:[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]$ ratio. CaCO_3 crystals were synthesized at room temperature by mixing CaCl_2 and Na_2CO_3 solutions. Reprinted from Bahrom et al. [73]. Copyright 2019, with permission from American Chemical Society.

route. They concluded that higher stirring times and speeds lead to the formation of more nuclei and, as a result, smaller crystals due to heterogeneous nucleation of the crystal growth. Just by varying the stirring time and speed, the authors were able to synthesize particles with sizes ranging between 3 and 20 μm . Other authors have also reported similar results [41,75].

Ševčík et al. [68] and Mori et al. [76] verified that when mixing precursor solutions with very high concentrations (1–2 M) the stirring speed is crucial for the type of the polymorph formed. Inadequate stirring creates different local concentrations in the same solution/gel, promoting the formation of calcite. On the other hand, a homogenous and continuous agitation results in the same salts concentration in the bulk and the formation of higher contents of vaterite.

The order of addition of reagents also affects the characteristics of the crystal. Wang et al. [77] demonstrated that adding the CO_3^{2-} ion solution to the Ca^{2+} ion solution (quick mixing or dropwise) results in smaller crystals with a uniform size distribution. However, with the opposite addition, the crystals become larger and have a non-uniform size distribution. This effect is more pronounced when the Ca^{2+} solution is added dropwise to the CO_3^{2-} solution. The different results are related to the different pH values of the precursor solutions [77,78]. When Ca^{2+} containing salts solutions ($\text{pH} \approx 6.41$ to 8.83 for CaCl_2 solutions with a concentration between 2 mM to 800 mM at 25 °C [65]) are added to CO_3^{2-} containing salts solutions ($\text{pH} \approx 11.0$ for Na_2CO_3 solutions with a concentration between 2 mM and 800 mM at 25 °C [65]) the transitory initial pH value, before reaching the equilibrium, is higher than when the opposite addition is done. This results in high nucleation rates with uncontrolled crystal growth and formation of large crystals with inhomogeneous size distribution [22,77].

2.2.5. Solvent

Water is the primordial, most used, and well-studied solvent for the synthesis of CaCO_3 . Nonetheless, mixtures of water with other solvents have also been used to form CaCO_3 crystals [45,48,73,79,80]. These solvents include ethanol, propranolol, methanol, polyethylene glycol (PEG), glycerine, *N,N*-dimethylformamide and EG [45,48,73,79–81]. Overall, the solvents decrease the solubility of CaCO_3 which results in higher supersaturation ratios and the formation of smaller particles. Some of these solvents like PEG, glycerine and EG also increase the density of the reaction media which diminishes the molecular diffusion and reduces the crystal growth rate and the probability of nucleation [73,79]. Moreover, low or no water content results in the stabilization of CaCO_3 particles formed at the early stages of the synthesis [73].

Solvents can also affect the type of polymorph formed. Sand K. et al. [45] demonstrated that the combination of water (50%) with ethanol (50%) promotes the formation of aragonite at 24 °C, which usually just

occurs at high temperatures in aqueous solutions.

2.2.6. Additives

Numerous articles have reported the effect of additives on the properties of CaCO_3 crystals. Nonetheless, additives use is mainly empirical due to their multiple roles that can be difficult to define. Moreover, the effect of additives on the properties of the crystals can depend on the additive concentration and other experimental conditions [82].

The type of additives tested on CaCO_3 synthesis include surfactants, synthetic polymers, biomolecules, biopolymers, and inorganic compounds. These compounds affect the crystallization process (cluster formation, prenucleation, nucleation, and growth), recrystallization kinetics, and can promote the formation of one polymorph form over the others. Moreover, it can lead to the formation of crystals with different sizes and shapes (flower, peanut, pyramid-like *etc.*) [21,22,82,83]. The incorporation of additives tries, to some extent, mimic the capacity of different organisms to build and control the formation of different CaCO_3 structures by combining it with organic or inorganic compounds (biomineralization) [22,84].

Reviews summarizing the effects of additives on the synthesis and stabilization of CaCO_3 can be found elsewhere [21,22,48]. Despite the large number of variables when studying the effect of additives, it has been reported that synthetic polymers, at the right concentration, usually induce the formation of vaterite spheres with a uniform size distribution. Polyacrylic acid (PAA) and polystyrene sulfonate (PSS) are reported as the most effective polymers in the retention of vaterite spherical shape [22,48]. Biopolymers and biomolecules such as cellulose, soluble starch, ovalbumin, bovine serum albumin, and dopamine are also known to promote the formation and/or stabilization of vaterite by adsorbing to the surface of the crystals, changing the surface energy and retarding the dissolution and recrystallization into calcite [21,22,48].

2.3. Approaches for loading molecules into CaCO_3 crystals

The three main approaches for loading the molecules of interest (MOI) into the CaCO_3 crystals are: adsorption, infiltration and co-precipitation [50,85,86]. More recently, freezing-induced loading, which can be considered a sub-type of infiltration, has been proposed as an efficient loading route [27].

2.3.1. Adsorption

This method corresponds to the adsorption of the molecule of interest on the surface of the crystals driven by molecular interactions (Fig. 7) [50]. This type of loading is universal for all CaCO_3 preparation approaches and is usually done by mixing CaCO_3 crystals with a solution containing the MOI [85]. pH is an important parameter when

adsorbing proteins into CaCO_3 as it affects the net charge of proteins and CaCO_3 , and consequently the electrostatic interactions as well as the activity of the proteins [34,47]. Interestingly, despite electrostatics governing the protein- CaCO_3 interaction, the crucial interactions for protein loading into the vaterite crystals are the inter-protein interactions in solution [87]. This is because protein aggregates, typically presented in protein solutions, can significantly affect protein diffusion into the porous vaterite crystals and this will determine protein loading as a whole [87].

The adsorption approach is easily done, although a very long mixing time might affect the stability of the CaCO_3 , mainly if a metastable polymorph is used. Moreover, adsorption presents a limited loading capacity [85].

2.3.2. Infiltration

The infiltration is based on mixing CaCO_3 crystals with the MOI followed by decreasing the MOI solubility by changing the pH or *via* solvent evaporation (Fig. 8) [50,88]. As well as adsorption, infiltration can be carried out utilising CaCO_3 crystals prepared by any of the different synthesis methods. However, this loading approach allows to load much higher quantities of the MOI than the adsorption approach, because the empty pores of the crystals can be completely occupied by the MOI [50,89,90].

Freezing-induced loading can be considered a sub-type of infiltration. This method involves mixing CaCO_3 crystals with the solution containing the MOI, which is then submitted to freezing/thawing cycles under agitation [27]. By controlling the number of cycles, the authors were able to load three to four times more nanoparticles and proteins, respectively, in comparison with the co-precipitation and adsorption methods.

2.3.3. Co-precipitation

The co-precipitation is based on capturing the MOI into the crystals during CaCO_3 synthesis by adding the MOI to the solutions of the precursor salts used (Fig. 9) [50,85]. This approach is widely used for the encapsulation into the crystals prepared by the solution precipitation and reverse emulsion methods. This is the most popular method for loading as it is quick, simple and allows to load very high amounts of MOI with a uniform distribution and at mild synthesis conditions [35,50,85]. Nonetheless, the cargo added during the synthesis might affect the crystallization process (nucleation rate, crystal polymorph type, crystal size and shape) and stability of CaCO_3 . Furthermore, while on one hand this approach can result in an enormous amount of MOIs loaded (more than 60% w/w for catalase), on the other hand the synthesis conditions (precursor salts and pH) can affect the activity of some MOIs like enzymes and proteins [34,36,89,91]. The loading of small molecules might also be problematic as they can easily diffuse through the pores of vaterite (mesoporous structure with typical pore

Fig. 7. Schematic representation of CaCO_3 crystals loading by adsorption. MOI - molecule of interest.

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of CaCO₃ crystals loading by infiltration. MOI - molecule of interest.

sizes of tens of nm). However, this can be suppressed by associating them with macromolecules [50]. An example includes loading mucin into vaterite crystals that brings extra charge into the cavity of the porous crystals making them effective for loading small drugs like doxorubicin [92–94].

2.4. Hybrid CaCO₃ crystals

The addition of additives during the synthesis of CaCO₃ can be applied to control the nucleation process and crystal stability, but also to improve the MOI loading efficiency and release profile. Coating CaCO₃ crystals with different polymers after synthesis can also be used to load, retain and control MOI release in a stimuli-responsive manner. Polyelectrolyte multilayers prepared by the layer-by-layer (LbL) deposition have been reported as an effective way to synthesize hybrid and polymer CaCO₃-based carriers for drug delivery.

Polyelectrolyte multilayers are very attractive coatings that can endow multiple functions including cellular adhesion and other bio-related activities serving as reservoirs for MOI [95–97]. The multilayers can reach thicknesses of micrometres and more [98], and host a very high amount of MOI including small charged molecules [99], large biomacromolecules such as proteins [100], and polysaccharides with rather small charge [101]. The multilayers performance can easily be tuned by changing the number of deposited layers, the type of polyelectrolytes used, including their combination, and the deposition

conditions such as temperature [102]. Potentially any decomposable particle (core), including protein aggregates, can be used for the production of multilayer structures [103–105]. CaCO₃ crystals have been used as sacrificial cores for the formation of free-standing multilayer capsules, as they can be easily decomposed with acidic compounds or Ca²⁺ chelating agents. The capsules can be stained by fluorescent probes bound to polyelectrolytes and the multilayers can be effective for protecting a loaded MOI and adjusting its release kinetics [106]. In general, the hybrid structures made of CaCO₃ crystals, polyelectrolyte multilayers, and soft polymer-based structures sensitive to external triggers [107], can serve as mimics of biological structures such as the extracellular matrix and the intracellular environment [108], or even be a key part of tailor-made polymer-based scaffolds used for tissue engineering [109–112]. This topic is, however, out of the main scope of the review and is only briefly mentioned to demonstrate the potential use of CaCO₃ crystals for design of polymer and hybrid structures as advanced drug delivery carriers.

3. CaCO₃ crystals as vectors for antimicrobials delivery

CaCO₃ presents a set of characteristics that makes it an excellent candidate for drug delivery including delivery of antimicrobials, as some of these therapeutic agents present limited stability, solubility, bioavailability, distribution/penetration, and short half-life. Different research works have explored the use of CaCO₃ as a vector for

Fig. 9. Schematic representation of CaCO₃ crystals loading by co-precipitation. MOI - molecule of interest.

Table 1
Summary of CaCO₃ synthesis conditions by carbonation and characteristics of the CaCO₃ crystals loaded with the antimicrobial agents.

Ref.	Synthesis conditions						Antimicrobials		Crystals characteristics		
	Synthesis method	Reagents (C _i before mix.)	Temp. (°C)	pH	Reaction time	Additives	Antimicrobial agent	Loading method	Morphology	Polymorph	Size
Pan et al. [113]	Carbonation	Ca(OH) ₂ (n.d.) CO ₂ - 40 ml.min ⁻¹	RT ^b	–	–	EDTA (n.d.)	Gentamicin sulfate (31.17 ± 1.66 to 50.05 ± 1.85 wt% ^a)	Adsorption	Chain-like	Calcite	62.5 nm
Sahoo P. et al. [114]	Carbonation	CaCl ₂ (0.3 M) NH ₄ OH (5 M) CO ₂ (99%)-1.5 l.min ⁻¹	RT ^b	–	30 min	Microalgae cells (1.8 wt %)	AgNPs (20-25 nm; 3.7 wt% ^a)	AgNPs <i>in situ</i> synthesis	Spherical	Calcite, vaterite	5 µm

RT: Room Temperature; C_i: initial concentration; mix: mixture; Temp.: Temperature; n.d.: not defined. AgNPs: Silver Nanoparticles.

^a Weight percentage of the antimicrobial agent in the total weight of the loaded CaCO₃ particles.

^b Calculated/Assumed based on the data/information presented in the article.

antimicrobials delivery. Tables 1–4 present a summary of the published research works in the area including the synthesis conditions, loading methods, and properties of the final CaCO₃ carriers. In the next sections, the application of the CaCO₃ crystals for antimicrobials delivery will be discussed in more detail.

3.1. Production of CaCO₃ vectors

As previously referred, there are a few different approaches for the synthesis of CaCO₃ crystals. In the works reporting the application of CaCO₃ crystals as carriers for antimicrobials the solution precipitation synthesis method was the most used. The microemulsion and carbonation methods were also reported, although not to such a great extent. Some works also presented a top-down approach for the production of micro- and nano-particles of CaCO₃ where cockle shells and eggshells were used as stocks [130,132,133]. Isa et al. [130] produced aragonite nanoparticles from cockle shells through a microemulsion (O/W) system using a high-pressure homogenizer for milling the particles. The particles were then loaded with ciprofloxacin by adsorption and tested against *Salmonella Typhimurium* ATCC 14028 by the disc diffusion susceptibility assay. The results demonstrated that the encapsulated ciprofloxacin presented higher antibacterial activity against *Salmonella Typhimurium* than the pristine ciprofloxacin with inhibitions zones of 18.6 ± 0.5 mm and 11.7 ± 0.9 mm, respectively. Another interesting top-down approach was reported by Apalangya et al. [132] who used eggshells waste for extraction of CaCO₃ and embedded proteins followed by *in situ* synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) by ball milling. This method allowed to decrease the size of CaCO₃ particles and the simultaneous reduction of Ag⁺ to Ag⁰ by the eggshell proteins (Fig. 10) also responsible for the stabilization of AgNPs.

The different routes of CaCO₃ synthesis, and their easy implementation and modification, broadens the spectrum of applications of CaCO₃ and highlights their suitability and adaptability for the encapsulation of different types of drugs.

3.2. Loading of antimicrobials

Tables 1–4 show various methods for loading antimicrobials into the CaCO₃ crystals. The most used methods were adsorption and co-precipitation due to their straightforwardness, efficiency and mild loading conditions.

The efficiency of antimicrobials loading is presented in the tables and ranged between 0.015 [125] and 50 wt% [113]. This wide range is explained by the enormous number of conditions that can potentially influence the loading capacity of the crystals: crystal synthesis and loading methods, additives used, crystals size, surface area, antimicrobial agent, etc.

Despite the advantages of the adsorption and co-precipitation loading methods due to their easy operation, some works have reported

very different and interesting loading approaches. To the best of our knowledge, Luca A. et al. [46,119,135] was the first group to report the use of CaCO₃ crystals as vectors for controlled delivery of antibiotics. In the different works published by the group, aragonite crystals were first synthesized and then the antimicrobials were loaded through integration by a cold isostatic pressing and sublimation process. As depicted in Fig. 11, the process starts by mixing aragonite powder with a pore-making agent (naphthalene) and the antibiotic of interest. Then the mixture is submitted to a cold isostatic pressing followed by heating under vacuum at 80 °C for the pore former elimination and the macroporosity induction [119,135].

The authors also tested the loading of the antibiotic gentamicin after aragonite processing with naphthalene. Nonetheless, the loading efficiency (Table 1) and release profiles were not satisfactory: 4 days against 8 to 12 days when gentamicin was incorporated during the aragonite processing [119].

Ferreira et al. [134] used a loading method that resembles the LbL assembly approach to produce multilayer capsules (Fig. 12). It consisted in coating the CaCO₃ crystals pre-coated with oppositively charged polymers, PSS and polyethyleneimine (PEI), with the biocide benzyltrimethyldecylammonium chloride (BDMDAC). The antimicrobial activity of the assembled particles was tested against *Pseudomonas fluorescens* due to its ability to form disinfectant-resistant biofilms. The CaCO₃ crystals coated with BDMDAC promoted a reduction of viable counts between 81.9 and 93.3% for 6.33 and 11.75 mg/l of BDMDAC, respectively. Similar results were obtained with free BDMDAC: 84.9% for 6.33 mg/l, and 91.3% for 11.75 mg/l. These results demonstrated that CaCO₃ did not affect the antibacterial activity of BDMDAC against *P. fluorescens*.

Sahoo P. et al. [114] fabricated and loaded AgNPs into CaCO₃ crystals (CaCO₃-AgNPs), previously synthesized by carbonation and using microalgae as bio-templates (Fig. 13).

The synthesized CaCO₃-AgNPs particles were then mixed with paints and tested against *Escherichia coli*, *Psychrobacter alimentarius*, and *Staphylococcus equorum* using the zone of inhibition test. The results demonstrated that while the unmodified paint did not present any antimicrobial activity, the paint mixed with CaCO₃-AgNPs did. Padmanabhuni R. and co-workers [131] reported a singular loading approach by combining adsorption with *in situ* synthesis. The research group coated CaCO₃ microcrystals with 4,4-dimethylhydantoin undecanoic acid (DMH-UA) and then treated the particles with diluted bleach for the synthesis of the antimicrobial agent 3-chloro-4,4-dimethylhydantoin undecanoic acid (Cl-DMH-UA).

All the works discussed in this section demonstrate the versatility of CaCO₃ loading routes, and that CaCO₃ crystals allow the application of very different approaches.

Table 2 Summary of CaCO₃ synthesis conditions by reverse microemulsion, and characteristics of the CaCO₃ crystals loaded with the antimicrobial agents.

Ref.	Synthesis conditions					Antimicrobials			Crystals characteristics			
	Synthesis method	Reagents (C _i before mix.)	Temp. (°C)	pH	Reaction time	Additives	Antimicrobial agent		Loading method	Morphology	Polymorph	Size
							Antimicrobial agent	Antimicrobial agent				
Qian et al. [115]	Reverse microemulsion	CaCl ₂ (1 M) Na ₂ CO ₃ (1 M)	RT ^b	-	-	-	Validamycin (11.1 to 19.3 wt% ^b)	Co-precipitation	Spherical	Calcite	57.5–199.7 nm	
Dizaj S. et al. [9]	Reverse microemulsion	CaCl ₂ (5 M) Na ₂ CO ₃ (2 M)	RT ^b	-	24 h	-	Ciprofloxacin HCl (20.49 ± 0.09 wt% ^b)	Co-precipitation or adsorption (10 min)	Spherical	Calcite, vaterite	90 nm (adsorption) 116 nm (co-precipitation)	
Dizaj S. et al. [11]	Reverse microemulsion	CaCl ₂ (5 M) Na ₂ CO ₃ (2 M)	25	-	24 h	-	Gentamicin Sulfate (25.3 ± 2.5 wt% ^b)	Co-precipitation or adsorption (10 min)	Spherical	Calcite, vaterite	90 nm (adsorption) 113 nm (co-precipitation)	
Memar Y. et al. [116]	Reverse microemulsion	CaCl ₂ (5 M) Na ₂ CO ₃ (2 M)	25	-	24 h	-	Gentamicin Sulfate (25.3 ± 2.5 wt% ^b)	Co-precipitation	Spherical	Calcite, vaterite	113 nm	

RT: Room Temperature; C_i: initial concentration; mix: mixture; Temp.: Temperature; n.d.: not defined.

^a Weight percentage of the antimicrobial agent in the total weight of the loaded CaCO₃ particles.

^b Calculated/Assumed based on the data/information presented in the article.

3.3. Properties of CaCO₃ vectors

CaCO₃ crystals can be presented as three different anhydrous polymorphs (calcite, vaterite and aragonite) and their size can be tuned by varying the synthesis conditions. The works reported in Tables 1–4 show that the crystals loaded with antimicrobials present different characteristic due to CaCO₃ sensitivity to the synthesis conditions such as the type of additive, pH, temperature, reagents ratios and concentrations. CaCO₃ crystals loaded with antimicrobials presented spherical, rhombohedral, needle-like, chain-like, and scalenohedral morphologies, with spherical shape being the most frequently reported. The three types of polymorphs were used as carriers with some articles reporting both vaterite and calcite polymorphs. The synthesis and loading conditions, including duration, are critical factors influencing the type of polymorph produced. The long synthesis and loading times reported in some of the works presented in Tables 1–4 might explain, in some cases, the predominance of calcite and calcite/vaterite mixtures over pure vaterite crystals, as bare vaterite and aragonite crystals can recrystallize to calcite by the dissolution and recrystallization pathways within hours [136,137].

Tables 1–4 show that the size of CaCO₃ crystals loaded with antimicrobial agents ranged between ca 14 nm and 10 μm. The vector size is an important parameter that can affect the pharmacokinetics of the whole system including the carrier distribution, extravasation/diffusion, endocytosis, flow properties, and clearance [138]. Therefore, the size of the crystals should be controlled based on their application especially if developed for human or animal use. Microparticles for subcutaneous or intramuscular administration generally present diameters up to 50 μm [139], nonetheless, for intravenous administration particles should have sizes between 30 and 300 nm as particles smaller than 10 nm are rapidly excreted by the kidneys and particles larger than 300 nm can promote thrombosis and be rapidly eliminated [140]. For pulmonary drug administration, the carriers optimum size ranges between 1 and 5 μm [138]. Smaller delivery systems present cytotoxic effects and are easily exhaled without promoting any therapeutic action. On the other side, particles with diameters larger than 5 μm are removed by the mucociliary clearance mechanism, not fulfilling their action [138]. The simplicity with which it is possible to adjust the size of CaCO₃ crystals by just changing few synthesis parameters (e.g., reagents concentration, stirring speed and time) makes the crystals attractive and dynamic drug delivery systems for different targets and routes of administration.

Islan G. and co-workers [117,118] published two works where CaCO₃ crystals with the optimal size for pulmonary delivery were developed. The hybrid vaterite microparticles, with sizes between 3 and 5 μm included sodium alginate (120 kDa) and/or high methoxyl pectin (70–75% esterification degree) [117,118]. A summary of the synthesis conditions and particle characteristic are present in Table 3. After synthesis the crystals were treated with alginate lyase (AL) for alginate cleavage (Fig. 14) resulting in particles with much higher surface area (71.6 to 74.9 m²/g) than the bare CaCO₃ (16.4 m²/g) and untreated crystals (34.9 to 51.4 m²/g) [117]. The developed particles were loaded with levofloxacin or levofloxacin/deoxyribonuclease (DNase) and tested against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 15442. The results demonstrated that the microparticles treated with AL present a potent bacterial inhibition resultant from the particles increased surface area and consequent higher levofloxacin content. Further *in vivo* experiments were carried out in mice to study the distribution and preclinical pharmacokinetics of the particles administrated in the lungs *via* nebulization and dry powder inhalation. The particles presented a good penetration resulting in higher levels of levofloxacin in comparison with the administration of the free drug form [118].

The tuneable properties of CaCO₃ crystals demonstrate their versatility to deliver drugs into different targets and the possibility to finely adjust their pharmacokinetic and release mechanism.

Table 3 Summary of CaCO₃ synthesis conditions by solution/colloidal precipitation, and characteristics of the CaCO₃ crystals loaded with the antimicrobial agents.

Ref.	Synthesis conditions					Antimicrobials			Crystals characteristics		
	Synthesis method	Reagents (C _i before mix.)	Temp. (°C)	pH	Reaction time	Additives	Antimicrobial agent	Loading method	Morphology	Polymorph	Size
Islan G. et al. [117]	Colloidal precipitation followed by AL treatment (48 h)	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.30 M) CaCl ₂ (0.29 M)	- ^b	10	5 min (CP) 48 h (AL treatment)	Glycine buffer; sodium alginate and/or pectin (6.5–23.6 wt %)	Levofloxacin (1.21 ± 0.01 to 1.40 ± 0.06 wt%)	Adsorption (24 h)	Spherical	Vaterite	3.6–4.6 µm
Islan G. et al. [118]	Colloidal precipitation followed by AL treatment (48 h)	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.30 M) CaCl ₂ (0.29 M)	- ^b	10	5 min (CP) 48 h (AL treatment)	Glycine buffer; sodium alginate (n.d.) and DNase (1.15–2.71 wt%)	Levofloxacin (7.41 wt%)	Adsorption (24 h)	Spherical	Vaterite	3–5 µm
Lucas et al. [46]	Solution precipitation	KHCO ₃ (0.1 M) CaCl ₂ (0.1 M)	100	-	-	-	Genamycin sulfate (n.d.); metronidazole (n.d)	Integration by CIP and sublimation	Needle-like	Aragonite	5–10 µm (L) 1 to 2 µm (W)
Lucas A. et al. [119]	Solution precipitation	KHCO ₃ (0.1 M) CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (0.1 M)	100	-	-	-	Genamycin sulfate: integration (5.5 ± 0.2 to 11.2 ± 0.6 wt%); adsorption (0.35 ± 0.02 to 0.40 ± 0.02 wt%)	Integration by CIP (5 min 600 MPa) and sublimation;	Needle-like	Aragonite	5–10 µm (L) 1 to 2 µm (W)
Yan H. et al. [120]	Solution precipitation	CaCl ₂ (2 mM) Na ₂ CO ₃ (2 mM)	0, 20, 40	-	24 h	Guar Gum (n.d.)	Vancomycin hydrochloride (24.3 to 46 wt%)	Adsorption (12 h)	Spherical	Calcite, vaterite	1 µm
Dizaj S. et al. [75]	Solution precipitation	Na ₂ CO ₃ (n.d.); CaCl ₂ (n.d.) molar ratios - 1:1; 3:1.5; 5:2	RT ^c	-	15 min	-	Gertamicin Sulfate (n.d.)	Co-Precipitation	-	-	80.0–300.12 nm
Begum et al. [26]	Solution precipitation	(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃ (n.d.); CaCl ₂ (n.d.) molar ratios - 1:1	RT	-	30 min	Poly (L-asp) and penta (L-lys) (n.d.)	Tetracycline (n.d.)	co-Precipitation	Spherical	Vaterite, amorphous	0.5–1 µm
Mihai et al. [121]	Solution precipitation	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.05 M) CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (0.10 M)	RT	10.5	9 h	PAH and/or pectins (n.d.)	Tetracycline hydrochloride (15.28–39.90 wt%)	Adsorption (4 h)	Rhombohedral and spherical	Calcite, vaterite	4.85–7.76 µm
Racovita et al. [122]	Solution precipitation	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.05 M) CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (0.10 M)	RT	10.5	8 h	PAH and/or pectins (n.d.)	Streptomycin (3.54–15.79 wt%); kanamycin (4.43–29.52 wt%)	Adsorption (4 h)	Rhombohedral and spherical	Calcite, vaterite	~5–8 µm
Said F. et al. [123]	Solution precipitation	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.33 M) CaCl ₂ (0.33 M)	RT ^c	-	3 min	-	Penicillin; ampicillin; ciprofloxacin (> 5 wt% ^b)	Adsorption (24 h)	Spherical	Calcite, vaterite	5 µm
Matei et al. [124]	Solution precipitation	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.4 M) CaCl ₂ (0.4 M)	10	-	30 min	<i>Ulva lactuca</i> extract (n.d.)	Ag/AgCl (n.d.)	Co-precipitation	Spherical or rhombohedral	Calcite	-
Dlugosz M. et al. [125]	Solution precipitation	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.03 M) Ca(NO ₃) ₂ (0.03 M)	25	-	5 min	PSS and PAH (after synthesis) (n.d.)	AgNPs (30–50 nm; 0.015 wt% ^a)	Co-precipitation	Spherical	-	2 µm
Baldassarre et al. [126]	Solution precipitation	NaHCO ₃ (0.125 M) CaCl ₂ (0.083 M)	-	-	-	-	Caffeic acid; N-acetylcysteine (n.d.)	Adsorption (overnight)	-	-	50–75 nm
Tessarolo L. et al. [127]	Solution precipitation	CaCl ₂ (0.025 M) Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.05 M)	30	-	72 h	SDS and Pluromic F-68 (n.d.)	Benznidazole (25 wt% ^a)	Co-Precipitation	Spherical	-	41.81 nm
Min K. et al. [128]	Solution precipitation	CaCl ₂ (0.044 M) ^c Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.044 M) ^c	RT	8	16 h	PEG-PASP (n.d.)	Doxycycline hyclate (2.35 wt% ^a)	Co-precipitation	Spherical	Vaterite	312.5 nm
Xue et al. [129]	Solution precipitation	CaCl ₂ (0.2 M) Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.2 M)	RT ^c	-	30 min	β-cyclodextrins; casein and Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles (n.d.)	Minocycline (n.d.)	Adsorption (24 h)	Spherical	Vaterite	2–5 µm

RT: Room Temperature; C_i: initial concentration; mix: mixture; Temp.: Temperature; n.d.: not defined; AL: Alginate lyase; CP: Colloidal precipitation; CIP: Cold isotactic pressing; L-Length; W-With; DNase: deoxyribonuclease; Poly(L-asp): Poly(L-aspartic acid sodium salt); penta(L-lys): Penta(L-lysine hydrobromide); PAH: Poly(allylamine hydrochloride); AgNPs: Silver Nanoparticles; PSS: Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate); PEG-PASP: poly(ethylene glycol)-poly(aspartic acid).
^a Weight percentage of the antimicrobial agent in the total weight of the loaded CaCO₃ particles.
^b Synthesis temperature is not specified, but the use of an ice bath is reported.
^c Calculated/Assumed based on the data/information presented in the article.

3.4. Release of antimicrobials

The antimicrobials currently used for the treatment of infectious diseases present some problems including short half-life, limited stability and solubility. Moreover, the therapeutic range of some drugs is narrow, as high concentrations can be toxic whereas low concentrations can promote the development of antimicrobial resistance [141,142]. Drug delivery systems can improve the pharmacokinetics of antimicrobial drugs by protecting and offering the control over their release in order to decrease dosage frequency, side effects and improve the therapeutic effect.

Drug delivery systems release the cargo through diffusion and/or carrier alterations in response to an intrinsic stimuli characteristics of pathological areas (pH, temperature, redox conditions and expression of certain enzymes) or an external stimuli applied deliberately (magnetic field, heat, light and ultrasound) [143]. CaCO₃ carriers can release the cargo via three ways: diffusion, carrier dissolution and recrystallization of the metastable polymorphs (vaterite and aragonite) to the more stable form, i.e., calcite. The drug release usually occurs by the three pathways, although the carrier and cargo properties and interactions, allied with the medium conditions as pH, chemical composition and temperature, will affect the primary release mechanism.

pH is a critical parameter on the CaCO₃ solubility. At low pH values free protons react with CO₃²⁻ forming HCO₃⁻ and consequently dissolving CaCO₃ crystals and therefore promoting the release of the drug. pH has been used as a trigger for CaCO₃ cargo release in acidic tumour microenvironments and inflammation sites [86,128,144].

Bacterial infection sites usually present low pH values due to increased amount of organic acids resultant from the anaerobic fermentation in certain bacteria and the host immune system response [145–147]. Together, the bacterial metabolism and the immune response can decrease the pH up to 5.5 [146]. Some of the works reporting the use of CaCO₃ crystals as antimicrobial carriers explore the pH sensitivity to trigger the drug release.

Min K. and co-workers [128] synthesized CaCO₃ nanoparticles loaded with doxycycline hyclate (DOXY) by co-precipitation using PEG-PA co-polymer as a mineralization template (Fig. 15). The goal was to synthesize pH-sensitive nanoparticles selective to the acidic micro-environment of bacterial biofilms. The drug release was tested at pH 7.4, 6.5, 5.5 and 4.0 resulting in ca 20, 60, 90 and 100%, respectively, of the drug being released after 24 h (Fig. 17). The results demonstrated the pH-dependent release behaviour of the carrier, with acidic pH triggering the release of DOXY due to an increased solubility of CaCO₃ at lower pH. The nanoparticles were tested against *Prevotella intermedia* ATCC49046, an anaerobic gram-negative bacterium known to cause oral diseases. The experiments were done at uncontrolled (~7.4–5.3) and controlled pH (~7.4–6.5) and with free and encapsulated DOXY. The results showed that the loaded (CaCO₃-DOXY) and free DOXY, at uncontrolled pH and after 25 h, had similar antibacterial activity, both presenting the same bactericidal concentration (1 µg/ml). On the other hand, at controlled pH, the drug loaded into CaCO₃ presented higher bactericidal concentration (2 µg/ml), demonstrating the nanoparticles sensitivity to pH. The crystal violet staining assay was also performed to investigate the inhibitory effect of DOXY-CaCO₃ on *Prevotella intermedia* biofilm formation. Once again, the pH-sensitivity was demonstrated with half of the antibiotic concentration significantly decreasing the biofilm formation at lower pH.

Qian et al. [115], synthesized calcite crystals loaded with validamycin by the reverse microemulsion method. The main synthesis conditions and crystals properties are present in Table 2. The release behaviour and stability of the free and encapsulated validamycin forms were tested at three different pH values: 5; 7 and 9. The results showed that validamycin loaded into CaCO₃ crystals presents better stability and a controlled release profile. At pH 5,7 and 9 almost all validamycin was released after 7 and 14 days demonstrating a pH-dependant release behaviour.

Table 4
Summary of the fabrication conditions for top-down method or previously acquired CaCO₃ crystals, and characteristics of the CaCO₃ crystals loaded with the antimicrobial agents.

Ref.	Fabrication conditions			Antimicrobials			Crystals characteristics		
	Method	Material	Temp. (°C)	Additives	Antimicrobial agent	Loading method	Morphology	Polymorph	Size
Isa et al. [130]	Top-down, microemulsion (O/W) milling with HPH	Dried cockle shells-CaCO ₃ powder	RT ^b	-	Ciprofloxacin HCl (5.9 wt%)	Adsorption (overnight)	Spherical	Aragonite	13.94–23.95 nm
Padmanabhuni R. et al. [131]	CA	CaCO ₃	-	-	Cl-DMH-UA (n.d.)	Adsorption of the Cl-DMH-UA precursor (2 h), Cl-DMH-UA <i>in situ</i> synthesis (1 h) (n.d.)	Scalenohedral	Calcite ^b	2–4 µm
Apalanga et al. [132]	Top-down	Eggshells	100	-	AgNPs (5–20 nm) (n.d.)	Adsorption and <i>in situ</i> AgNPs synthesis (2 h)	-	Calcite	Micron range
Timob B. et al. [133]	Top-down	Eggshells	-	-	AgNPs (10–15 nm) (n.d.)	Adsorption and <i>in situ</i> AgNPs synthesis (≥ 5 h)	-	Calcite	-
Ferreira et al. [134]	CA	CaCO ₃	-	PSS and PEI (n.d.)	Benzyl/dimethyl/dodecylammonium chloride (n.d.)	LbL adsorption	Spherical	-	2–4 µm

CA: CaCO₃ acquired from and external supplier; RT: Room Temperature; Temp.: Temperature; n.d.: not defined; AgNPs: Silver Nanoparticles; PSS: Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate); Cl-DMH-UA: 3-chloro-4,4-dimethylhydantoin undecanoic acid; LbL: Layer by Layer; PEI: Polyethyleneimine.

^a Weight percentage of the antimicrobial agent in the total weight of the loaded CaCO₃ particles.

^b Calculated/Assumed based on the data/information presented in the article.

Fig. 10. Proposed mechanism of CaCO₃-AgNPs nanocomposites formation. Reprinted from Apalangya et al. [132]. Copyright 2014, with permission from Elsevier.

Długosz M. and co-workers [125] fabricated CaCO₃ vectors loaded with AgNPs by co-precipitation and then used the particles for coating down feathers. The AgNPs release profile from CaCO₃ particles was evaluated at two different pH values, *i.e.*, 6.8 and 5.4 over 14 days (Fig. 17). The results demonstrated a slow and pH-dependant release of silver and, as expected, at pH 5.4 silver was released more quickly.

Begum G. and co-workers [26] developed CaCO₃ structures using poly(L-aspartic acid sodium salt) (poly(L-asp)), and penta(L-lysine hydrobromide) (penta(L-lys)) as templates for spherical particles formation, and tetracycline entrapment (Fig. 15).

Tetracycline release behaviour was evaluated over 15 days at three different pH values (4.5, 6.0, and 7.4) and at 37 °C (Fig. 16). Regardless of the pH, an initial burst release of the drug was verified followed by a controlled release of almost all the loaded antibiotic within 24 h at pH 4.5 (100% released) and 360 h at pH 6 (94% released). The drug release at pH 7.4 was comparatively slower with 61% of the drug being released after 360 h. This and the other research works presented in this section demonstrate the pH-sensitivity of CaCO₃ carriers, with low pH values being able to trigger CaCO₃ dissolution and consequent drug release.

Fig. 11. Steps for the fabrication of porous aragonite-based materials. Reprinted from Luca A. et al. [46]. Copyright 2001, with permission from Elsevier.

Fig. 12. Representation of the layer-by-layer assembly method used to produce CaCO₃ microparticles coated with BDMDAC. Figure redrawn based on the work of Ferreira et al. [134].

3.5. Biocompatibility of CaCO₃ vectors

The application of drug delivery systems depends on the safety that they present to the patients. Therefore, their biocompatibility assessment is of utmost importance.

Up to now, all *in vitro* studies suggest no cytotoxicity of bare vaterite crystals [148] even when used at high concentrations [149]. Although there is still a limited number of *in vivo* studies on CaCO₃ use, all of them suggest safe administration of CaCO₃ particles as drug carriers *via* different routes, e.g. ocular [36], intranasal [150], pulmonary [151] or transdermal [152]. Interestingly, it has been demonstrated that bolus intravenous injections of bare CaCO₃ crystals can alter the extracellular pH and can be used to inhibit tumour growth *in vivo* [153]. Besides, different works have tested the biocompatibility of CaCO₃ carriers loaded with antimicrobials. Memar M. et al. [116] synthesized CaCO₃ nanoparticles loaded with gentamicin sulfate by a reverse microemulsion method and tested their biocompatibility and cytotoxicity. Biocompatibility was accessed using three assays: i) haemolysis assays on human red blood cells, ii) erythrocyte sedimentation rate assay and iii) protein interaction between loaded CaCO₃ and human blood plasma. The toxicity was tested by the 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) viability assay on a hBM-MSC cell line. The reported results demonstrated that the CaCO₃ nanoparticles loaded with gentamicin sulfate displayed a favourable biocompatibility and low toxicity.

Isa et al. [130] tested the biocompatibility and cytotoxicity of aragonite particles loaded with ciprofloxacin in a Macrophages J774A.1 cell line using three different tests: i) MTT (viability test), ii) bromo-21-deoxyuridine assay (genotoxicity test) and iii) interleukin 1 beta cellular expression assessment by RNA extraction and reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction, (immunogenicity assessment). The results demonstrated that the loaded nanoparticles presented cytocompatibility without the upregulation of the immune system response.

The *in vivo* biocompatibility, resorption and bone ingrowth of aragonite microparticles was evaluated by Lucas et al. [46]. The results demonstrated an excellent biocompatibility, resorption and osteoconduction with the porosity degree largely affecting the last two properties. Overall, the results demonstrated the enormous potential of

this type of material as a resorbable bone substitute and its good biocompatibility.

3.6. Antimicrobial performance

The key goals when using antimicrobials delivery systems are to protect the antimicrobials from degradation, decrease the toxicity and promote a controlled release while assuring a therapeutic concentration at the site of infection. Table 5 presents a comparison between the antimicrobial activity of the free and immobilized antimicrobial agents. In most of the reported studies the compounds loaded into CaCO₃ crystals presented similar or better antimicrobial activity than the free form. Several factors can alter the antimicrobial activity of the compounds loaded into CaCO₃ particles such as the size and morphology of the crystals, presence of additives, affinity between the CaCO₃ and the cargo, type of microorganism, microenvironment conditions (pH, temperature, composition and ionic strength) and even the type of antimicrobial assay used.

Apalangya et al. [132] produced CaCO₃ particles with embedded AgNPs and tested the free and loaded AgNPs against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 11775 by a modified Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion assay. The results indicated a superior antibacterial activity of the AgNPs loaded into CaCO₃ particles. The authors explained this effect by a better dispersion and interaction of the particles with *E. coli* improved by the hydrophilic groups of the eggshell proteins present in the vectors. Isa et al. [130] also reported better antimicrobial activity against *Salmonella Typhimurium* ATCC 14028, of ciprofloxacin loaded into aragonite. The authors proposed that the higher antibacterial activity resulted from a higher diffusion of the nanoparticles through the bacteria. Tessarolo L. et al. [127] published one of the few works where an antiparasitic drug, benznidazole (BZN), is encapsulated into CaCO₃ crystals (BZN-CaCO₃). The encapsulated and free drug was tested against *Trypanosoma cruzi* strain Y, a parasite responsible for the Chagas disease. The results demonstrated a higher potency of BZN-CaCO₃ particles against the three forms of *Trypanosoma cruzi* (epimastigote, trypomastigote and amastigote). The authors proposed that the better activity of BZN-CaCO₃ particles resulted from an increased cell permeability when compared with the free BZN form. Pan et al. [113] produced calcite nanoparticles

Fig. 13. Synthesis steps of porous CaCO₃ microspheres by carbonation in the presence of microalgae. Silver nanoparticles were synthesized on the porous micro-particles by reducing [Ag(NH₃)⁺] with D-maltose. Figure redrawn based on the work of Sahoo P. et al. [114].

Fig. 14. SEM images of CaCO₃-sodium alginate microparticles before (left) and after (right) being treated with alginate lyase. Figure adapted from Islan C. et al. [117]. The plot profile of the microparticles surface is shown in the top right corner of the images. Copyright 2015, with permission from Elsevier.

loaded with gentamicin sulfate and tested the antibacterial activity of bare calcite, free and encapsulated gentamicin against *Bacillus subtilis*. The results demonstrated a synergistic effect between CaCO₃ and the gentamicin sulfate. The authors propose that the drug delivery system increased the damage of the bacterial cells wall and enhanced the permeability of the cell membranes. The synergistic effect was not reported by Dizaj S. et al. [9] and Memar et al. [116] who also studied the encapsulation of gentamicin in CaCO₃ particles and verified that the

bare antibiotic presented similar and better antibacterial properties, respectively. The different results can be explained by the different properties of the carriers (size, morphology, porosity), experimental conditions and bacterium type.

Min K. et al. [128] and Padmanabhuni R. et al. [131] also reported inferior antibacterial activity of the antimicrobial agents loaded into CaCO₃ particles at some of the experimental conditions studied. In the case of Min K. et al. [128] the lower bactericidal activity of the

Fig. 15. Illustration of DOXY-loaded CaCO₃ (DOXY-MNPs) synthesis pathway (a) and DOXY release mechanism from the MNPs triggered by the acidic micro-environment of the biofilm (b). EPS: exopolysaccharides. Reprinted from Min K. et al. [128]. Copyright 2019, with permission from Elsevier.

Fig. 16. Tetracycline entrapment process and CaCO_3 mineralization and assembly. Adapted from Begum et al. [26]. Copyright 2016, with permission from American Chemical Society.

encapsulated doxycycline hyclate was verified at a higher pH values (7.4–6.5) but not at lower ones (7.4–5.3) as discussed in Section 3.4. Regarding the work of Padmanabhuni R. et al. [131], the inferior antibacterial activity was related with the lower mobility of the antimicrobial agent on the CaCO_3 particles, with free Cl-DMH-UA presenting better results due to its higher mobility. Nonetheless, when free and encapsulated Cl-DMH-UA were incorporated into cellulose acetate films as antimicrobial fillers, both presented similar activity against *S. aureus* regardless of the concentration, and against *E. coli* at 5% w/w. Moreover, both systems presented a similar biofilm growth inhibition.

Overall, CaCO_3 has a high potential as a vector for delivery of antimicrobial agents as it can protect and promote a controlled release without affecting the antimicrobial activity.

4. Current challenges and future opportunities

CaCO_3 crystals present a set of characteristics desirable for drug carriers including biocompatibility, controlled release, low-cost and simple fabrication. Several works have studied the application of CaCO_3 crystals loaded with antimicrobial agents for different applications. Some of these research studies propose the use of the vectors for antimicrobial coatings, fillers for polymeric composite materials [125,131,133], water filtration [132], osteomyelitis treatment and bone grafting [9,11,46,116,119], treatment of respiratory infections [117,118], antimicrobial filler for paints [114], oral infections treatment [128], biocides delivery into olive trees [126], and treatment of skin burns [124]. The diverse applications reported up to now demonstrate the versatility of CaCO_3 crystals.

Fig. 17. pH-responsive release of doxycycline (top left), AgNPs (top right) and tetracycline (bottom) from CaCO_3 carriers. Adapted from Min K. et al. [128], Długosz M. et al. [125], and Begum et al. [26], respectively. Copyright 2019, 2012 and 2016, with permission from Elsevier, Springer Nature and American Chemical Society, respectively.

Table 5
Summary of the antimicrobial activity of the free and CaCO₃-encapsulated antimicrobial agents.

Ref.	Microorganism	Antimicrobial agent (AA)	Antimicrobial activity (Free-AA)	Antimicrobial activity (CaCO ₃ -AA)	Result type
Pan et al. [113]	<i>B. subtilis</i>	Gentamicin sulfate	–	+	GI
Qian et al. [115]	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	Validamycin	+ (2nd day) – (7th day)	– (2nd day) + (7th day)	GI
Dizaj S. et al. [9]	<i>S. aureus</i>	Ciprofloxacin HCl	SA	SA	MIC
Dizaj S. et al. [11]	<i>S. aureus</i>	Gentamicin sulfate	SA	SA	MIC
Memar Y. et al. [116]	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Gentamicin sulfate	+	–	MIC
Begum et al. [26]	<i>B. subtilis</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>K. pneumoniae</i> , and <i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Tetracycline	SA	SA	MBC MIC and ZI
Tessarolo L. et al. [127]	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i> strain Y	Benznidazole	– (24 h) SA (72 h)	+ (24 h) SA (72 h)	IC ₅₀
Min K. et al. [128]	<i>Prevotella intermedia</i>	Doxycycline hyclate	– SA +	+ SA –	LC ₅₀ BC (pH 7.4–5.32) BC (pH 7.4–6.5)
Isa et al. [130]	<i>Salmonella Typhimurium</i>	Ciprofloxacin HCl	–	+	ZI
Padmanabhuni R. et al. [131]	<i>S. aureus</i> and <i>E. coli</i>	Cl-DMH-UA	+ SA (<i>S. aureus</i>) + (<i>E. coli</i> : 1–3 wt% ^a) SA (<i>E. coli</i> : 5 wt% ^a) SA	– SA (<i>S. aureus</i>) – (<i>E. coli</i> : 1–3 wt% ^a) SA (<i>E. coli</i> : 5 wt% ^a) SA	SR SR (CA) SR (CA) BGI
Apalanga et al. [132]	<i>E. coli</i>	AgNPs (5–20 nm)	–	+	ZI
Ferreira et al. [134]	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Benzylidimethyldecylammonium chloride	SA	SA	SR

AA: Antimicrobial Action; SA: Similar Antimicrobial Activity; (–): Inferior Antimicrobial Activity; (+) Superior Antimicrobial Activity; GI: Growth Inhibition; MIC: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration; MBC: Minimum Biofilm Inhibitory Concentration; ZI: Zone of Inhibition; IC₅₀: Inhibitory Concentration that inhibits 50% of growth; LC₅₀: Lethal Concentration that causes the death of 50% of the microorganisms; BC: Bactericidal Concentration; SR: Survival Ratio; CA: Cellulose Acetate (free and encapsulated forms used as cellulose acetate additive); Cl-DMH-UA: 3-chloro-4,4-dimethylhydantoin undecanoic acid; BGI: Biofilm Growth Inhibition.

^a Cl-DMH-UA weight percentage on the total weight of the cellulose acetate film.

While CaCO₃ can work as a vector that protects the drugs from the external environment and prolongs their half-life, it can also be designed to release the cargo in a controlled way and on demand (at required specific conditions). One of the most exciting characteristics of the CaCO₃ crystals is their sensitivity to different pH values which allows the cargo to be released in specific sites or conditions. Min K. and co-workers [128] published a detailed work where pH sensitivity was used for the smart release of antibiotics. This is a fascinating topic and despite the significant advances that have been demonstrated, there is still work to be done to tune the pH sensitivity in a way that the cargo is released at a specific and narrow pH range. One possible solution to overcome this is the association of the CaCO₃ crystals with additives that can mediate the solubility of the crystals.

CaCO₃ presents three anhydrous polymorphs (calcite, vaterite and aragonite) which have been applied as carriers for antimicrobials with very attractive results. Interestingly, despite vaterite being one of the most attractive carriers for drugs, the works reporting the use of CaCO₃ as antimicrobial carriers do not show a preference for this polymorph (Tables 1–5). While in some works the use of a polymorph type is deliberated, in other reports it is unclear why a certain polymorph or a mixture of polymorphs is chosen. It would be attractive to use vaterite in more scientific works due to its unique features. Research work where the three polymorphs are compared as carriers for the same drug at similar experimental conditions would also be desirable.

Another topic not systematically studied yet is the effect of CaCO₃ crystal sizes on the antimicrobial activity. Carriers size is a crucial characteristic as it affects the interactions with the microorganisms and the ability to cross the cell membranes. There are various works where CaCO₃ crystals with micro- and nano-sizes are used for antimicrobials delivery but there aren't reports where the comparison of crystals with different sizes is done. Studies on this topic would allow to optimize the therapeutic effect of CaCO₃ crystals as antimicrobials carriers.

Finally, some critically ill patients require the use of different antimicrobial agents concomitantly [154,155]. All the research work discussed in this review used CaCO₃ carriers for the transportation of a

single therapeutic agent, with the exception of Islan G. et al. [118] report, who associated an antibiotic (levofloxacin) with a mucolytic agent (DNase). It would be of interest to study the advantages of combining different therapeutic agents in the same carrier and ultimately to develop vectors able to increase the therapeutic effect. Such works may appear in nearest future and this review can stimulate the progress towards this direction.

5. Conclusion

CaCO₃ crystals present an enormous potential as carriers for antimicrobials. Crystal synthesis allows the fabrication of particles with different sizes, morphologies, surface area and physical-chemical properties using different adjustable affecters such as pH, temperature, reagents ratios and additives. The capacity to host and protect high amounts of various antimicrobials and to deliver them in a controlled, and in some cases, in a stimuli-response fashion proves the versatility of the crystals as modern and advanced drug delivery systems. Several works have explored the use of CaCO₃ as carriers for delivery of antimicrobial agents with studies demonstrating a pH-dependent controlled release without affecting the antimicrobial activity and, in some cases, even improving it. The use of CaCO₃ as carriers for multiple drugs opens new avenues for combating multidrug resistance which nowadays is one of the major obstacles for successful antimicrobial therapies. The different approaches reported so far for loading CaCO₃ particles with antimicrobials demonstrates their high versatility, with the synthesis variations being almost endless. Moreover, the simple synthesis methods and affordable reagents, makes them highly attractive when compared with carriers that require long, complex and expensive fabrication methods. The good biocompatibility results anticipate their safety in humans, a determinant factor for their introduction in the market as drug delivery systems. In this context, more efforts on the evaluation of the cytotoxicity, pharmacokinetics and possible side effects of CaCO₃-based delivery vectors are expected in the nearest future. Although the research on this topic is still relatively new, and has only

reached the pre-clinical stage, current usage of CaCO₃ as a food supplement and as a pharmaceutical additive approved by the FDA might significantly accelerate its further approval for drug delivery and smooth the bench-to-market translation. There is also some work to be done regarding the optimization and programmed release of antimicrobials, which will potentiate the therapeutic effect and increase the scope of applications. This includes improving the pH sensitivity to specific and narrow pH ranges. The study of the effect of the different polymorphs, their size and charge on the transportation, release and antimicrobial activity will also be important to optimize the therapeutic effect. Despite all the challenges reported, the positive results reported so far sign the potential of CaCO₃ as extremely attractive and efficient antimicrobial carriers. We strongly believe that research towards CaCO₃-based carriers with multiple antimicrobials, and externally triggered or/and programmed release, will fill the gap in the development of antimicrobial delivery systems, and allow to overcome the serious problem of antimicrobial resistance.

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